

The Bangladeshi Consumer Behavior and Attitude Toward Superstores

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Abstract

Superstores introduced a whole new experience in the shopping of daily necessities. They offered quality products at a stable price in safe and clean environment in order to survive and achieve profitability. Although there are many factors which relate to customer satisfaction, but most of previous empirical research in this field tended to emphasize on quality products, products variety and special products, location, hygienic environment, hassle free shopping and freshness, competitive price, service and layout of the store. The purpose of the study is to identify the role of each of the factors to respond to customer requirements to satisfy customers and what and how they behave in the market place toward these factors. The totality of their movement toward the factors and attitude, the researcher liked to demonstrate here. The questionnaires were developed from many previous researches. The data was collected from 50 customers of 5 superstores in Chittagong. The result of this study shows that the factors have positive relationship with customer satisfaction those in terms ensure store loyalty. Therefore, the superstores should consider product and store service factors as the foundation to satisfy customer and to improve service quality as an add-on value to customer.

Keywords: Superstore, Consumer Behaviour, Attitude, Demographic factors.

1.1 Introduction

Organized retail is booming and creating huge opportunity for enterprises. Retailers though sell other companies' products work out their own marketing strategies fixing their own target market towards providing customer satisfaction separately. Retail stores irrespective of product line and relative prices emerge in all shape and sizes, such as Specialty stores, Department stores, Supermarkets, Superstore, Convenience stores, Discount stores and Off-price stores (Armstrong, 2006; Rahul, 2007; Jeevananda, 2011). With the aggressive growth plans of super center competition and a fragmented state of the grocery stores are being faced with new challenges (Mc Taggart, 2004). In this perspective, McKinsey suggested considerable factors for retail business are range, price, expertise, convenience and experience. Out of the factors, price has comparatively much importance in any business strategy in the dynamic business environment. Moreover, today's retailing revolutionizing through online influence investors and entrepreneur to revamp accordingly to be effective with understanding the customer behavior. It is also worth mentioning that price element and the factors related to dramatize revolution should keep in mind to the retailers or service providers (Rahul, 2007; Nagle and Holden, 2002).

Customer satisfaction foot-print is routed with customer expectations and the actual service experience. The degree of satisfaction equates through their nature and crossing tendencies. Marketing scientists prove that satisfying and keeping current customers is more profitable than having to win new ones. Undoubtedly, this is the key factor to focus and to success for any retail store or business. To pay heed on the degree of satisfaction, the factors affecting satisfaction are very imperative to both service-oriented and product-oriented organizations to discern because satisfied customers are most likely to be loyal and to ensure repeat orders (Kotler, 2010; Jeevananda, 2011).

1.2 Literature Review

1.2.1 History of Supermarket:

Supermarket diffusion in developing countries has occurred in three waves, so far, starting in the 1990s with much of South America, East Asia (outside China) and South Africa. This was followed by a second wave in the mid-to-late 1990s, including Mexico, Central America and much of Southeast Asia. In the late 1990s and early 2000s, a third wave hit China, India and Vietnam (www.wikipedia.com).

According to Thomas Reardon, a professor at the Department of Agricultural, Food and Resource Economics at Michigan State University, Bangladesh is part of a fourth wave that just barely has emerged in the last few years.

Other countries at a similar stage are Cambodia, Bolivia and certain countries in West Africa. The American researcher feels it is likely that the diffusion of supermarkets will be quite slow for the fourth wave, compared to the first three waves. The reason is that the key socioeconomic changes necessary for a change in the retail environment are happening in Bangladesh at a pace much slower than, for example, in India (Dieter Bachmann, 2010; BSOA, 2011). These changes acting as a driving force behind supermarket diffusion include increasing urbanization, increasing number of women working outside their home (which leaves them with less time for shopping of essentials), and increasing incomes per capita.

By the estimates of Ashok Gulati, director of International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI), it will probably take another decade or two, until supermarket diffusion in a country like Bangladesh is appreciable, meaning that roughly around 20 to 25 percent of retail sales are made through this channel. “But the time for South Asia seems to have come,” he adds. “Just look at the expansion of Cargills Ceylon in Sri Lanka.” That retailer has more than 120 food-supermarkets all over the country (Dieter Bachmann, 2010; BSOA, 2011). In fact, Sri Lanka with a population of over 20 million people has 240 supermarkets, while Dhaka with its 15 million inhabitants does not even have 50 such stores. Not so quickly though in the developing countries like Bangladesh, it was only in 2001 that the first supermarket got started in the capital city Dhaka by the name and style of Agora. Closely followed by Nandan to make a mention. Other smaller ones sprang up on the success of the trend setters, out of which Agora, Meena Bazar, CENTEL, Fresh N’ Near, PQS five, Prince Bazar, Nandan and Swapno are worth mentionable.

1.2.2 Current Market Scenario:

Superstores are set to boom in the country as the current market players are planning to open several hundred more outlets in the next few years to cope with the rising demand from the consumers. With a strong 15-20 per cent annual sales growth, about 30 companies with more than 200 outlets have already made foray into the industry. The annual turnover of the superstores now stands at around Tk 15.0 billion (1500 crore), according to Bangladesh Supermarket Owners Association (BSOA). Hassle-free shopping environment, hygienic commodities, fresh vegetables, meat and fish at the supermarkets are earning appreciation of the customers. The supermarket biggies have attempted the massive expansion drive to attract the shoppers, who still depend on unplanned wet markets to buy their daily essentials. They say that a rise in organized retailing would offer the consumers hygienic foods at competitive prices, compared to those offered by retailers in the kitchen markets, where commodities are sold mostly in unhygienic condition. But a decade ago, the retail-level trade was in the hands of thousands of small traders in the wet markets and the grocery shops in cities and remained out of the focus of the big business houses. In the past decade, many small and big supermarkets made debut, successfully attracting middle and upper middle class consumers, a section of whom are gradually turning to chain stores from the wet or kitchen markets, one of the superstore operators say. So far, the pace of expansion of the existing key-players in the supermarket business has been rather slow. Agora, Meena Bazar, Nandan and PQS have no more than a handful of stores. Many plan to expand their business, but quite a few difficulties arise when launching a superstore-chain in Bangladesh. From the all existing, Dhaka-based Agora now runs four outlets, Meena Bazar nine including seven in Dhaka, PQS five, Prince Bazar two, Nandan five and Swapno 70 including 30 outside the capital. Bangladesh Rifles (BDR) also runs 11 stores in the capital.

“It is a good sign. Expansion of outlets will boost consumer’s confidence and help create a market for manufacturers,” Niaz Rahim, president of BSOA. He also said once the supermarket culture is established, the commodity prices also will stabilize. The supermarket culture is playing a vital role in generating employment, with a single store providing jobs to around 50 people, said N. Rahim. “The massive expansion plan by various market players will open the door for more employment opportunities.” Due to massive expansion of superstores, farmers will no more be needed to turn to the multi-level intermediation as they will directly contact the chain stores operators. “As a result, they will no more be cheated,” Zakir Hossain, general secretary of BSOA. Mr Hossain lamented that they did not get the required assistance from the government, although they were paying taxes. “It requires Tk 60-70 million to open a small-size store,” he added. (Monira Munni, March 5, 2010.). Organised retailers in the country are focusing more on strengthening their backward linkage supply chain, a challenge faced by retail chain shops for products availability. As the superstore concept is not very traditional the superstore biggies have failed to grow accordingly mainly due to proper and sufficient supply chain management, top retailers said. The most organised and disciplined retailers are trying to maintain their own supply chain management to bring fresh and quality products to the store in urban area from root level farmers directly. (Monira Munni, October 30, 2010). Syed

Ferhat Anwar, who teaches marketing at Institute of Business Administration at Dhaka University, said a rise in supermarkets would give consumers more choices and allow them to choose independently. “It will increase consumption and help boost economy,” he said, “But the question is if the market is going to be saturated for too much increase in the number of supermarkets.” Ferhat however said organized retail shops might lead to an improvement in quality and services in the wet markets. (Sohel Parvez, 2009).

However, a majority of Bangladesh customers will not change their shopping habits anytime soon. At least this is what the leading academic researchers in this field view.

1.3 Objectives

This study aims to portrait present condition and opportunities of supermarket culture and also the customer’s opinions toward different services provided by existing supermarkets. But the specific objectives of this study are –

- i. To constitute Customer profile by demographic data, such as identification (name, address, and phone no.), sex, marital status, name of family members, ages, income, occupation, no. of children present, home ownership, length of residence, no. and make of car owns.
- ii. To identify factors that lead consumers to shop at specific superstore and the impact of location for the same.
- iii. To uncover the relative importance attached to each of the factors selected as the choice criteria utilized in selecting a department store.
- iv. To discover Attitude of customers toward specific superstore toward product quality, product assortment, customer services, services of the store personnel, and the like.
- v. To find out the mostly shopping items particularly from the superstore.
- vi. To trace out the degree of customer satisfaction, store loyalty and the recommendation to others.
- vii. To calculate rating of the stores by their customer.

Furthermore, the study will help the sponsors to determine consumer perceptions and preferences for the superstore, and areas of weakness identified in terms of specific factors influencing choice criteria

1.4 Methodology

At the very outset to single out the aspects of the subject matter, two types of data sources were utilized. In this way, the abstracting and indexing journals published or unpublished were selected as first place to go. Academic journals, annual report, BSOA (Bangladesh Supermarket Owners Association) reports, conference proceedings, government reports, books and finally the current and available information from the newspapers were tapped depending upon the nature of the problem. The primary data were collected particularly through survey. The selected sample superstores were only five in numbers namely Khulshi Mart, Swapno, Well Mart, Agora and Meena Bazar, and samples selected bases are the availability of the varieties of essential commodities, Household, Home appliances, Cosmetics & Toiletries, Meat & Fish, Fruits, Groceries, Dairy, Bakery, Vegetables, and other necessities at the stores. The no. of respondents is at least 10 customers from each of the superstore and selected randomly that is convenience sampling. Hence, 50 is the sample size in total. There were many survey respondents that left certain questions blank and consequently the frequency distributions do not add to the total number of customers surveyed the calculated percentages reflect only portions of the answers to the question. The respondents were met during shopping (Mall intercept personal interview technique) as well as after or before shopping which one found suitable. After the data collection, the raw data were categorized through coding, tabulation and drawing statistical inferences based on the computation of various percentages and averages etc. by applying various well defined statistical formulae like arithmetic mean and relative frequency as well.

1.5 Analysis and Findings

1.5.1.1 Customers Demographic Profile (Age-wise sample participant) [Table # 1 (a)]

All age’s people ranging from 18 years to 48 years or over were purchased commodities from superstores where maximum no. of respondents (32%) from 28-32 years, and then 20% from 23-37 years, 16% from 33-37 years, 12% from 18-22 years, and 10% from 43-47 years. Though age groups are almost undifferentiated in all the sample superstores but the customers aged between 18 to 22 years are frequently purchase from the Khulshi-mart and again they have so many foreign customers living near especially Srilankan.

1.5.1.2 Customers Demographic Profile (Customers Qualification, Gender and Marital Status) [Table # 1 (b)]

74% of the total respondents are female and rest of male. Again married person visibility is 66% comparing with single or others at 34%. The qualification has indicated that the educated people like to get the taste to shop at superstore.

1.5.1.3 Customers Demographic Profile (Occupation, Credit Card Usage and Car Owns) [Table # 1 (c)]

It is seen that maximum no. of customers is married (66%) and they are mostly from the female side (74%), and from the occupation point of view they are housewife (48%). Students (26%) are also enthusiastic to purchase goods from superstore. Again, it is seen that maximum no. of sample customers (72%) is not owned cars and a few of them use credit card (26%), does not mean that the customers who owns car and use credit cards do not purchase from the superstore. Actually the tradition of upper class as only the customer of superstore has been changed.

1.5.1.4 Customers Demographic Profile (Experience Customer Base, Purchase frequency in a typical week & Level of Income) [Table # 1 (d)]

Owing to maximum numbers of customers, both Well Mart and Meena Bazar have most experienced (more than 2 years) customers bearing 55% of their own customers, then Shwapno's 44% customers have experienced for 1 to 2 years, in Khulshi Mart, 50% of 6 month to 1 year, in Agora- 44% of less than 6 month experience. On an average, 35% customers have 1 to 2 years experience to purchase from superstore. Again, 38% of the sample customers usually purchase 1 or 2 times in a week, 28% less than once, 10% 3 or 4 times, and 12% frequently purchase. Again 12% of overall customers purchases more frequently i.e. more than 4 times in a week. Being considering specific category, the customers of the age group between 28-32 years purchase 1 or 2 times (16% of the total respondents). Considering the maximum no. of customer:

- Aged 18-22 years buys less than once in a week (10%),
- Aged 23-27 years buys not more than 2 times in a week (12%), and
- Aged 33-37 years buys less than once in a week (8%).

Furthermore, Maximum no. of sample customers' average income varies between tk. 20000 to tk. 80000, where tk. 40000 to tk. 60000 is 32% and 30% is for tk. 20000 to tk. 40000 and 24% owns tk. 60000 to tk. 80000.

1.5.2 Mostly Purchasing Product from each super store [Table # 2]

From overall consideration, the maximum no. of sample customers purchases cosmetic and toiletries from the sample superstores due to the age group responding most between 18-32 years and carries 64% of the total respondents. Bakery and, Fish and Meat are also the most selling products at superstores. But considering each superstore most selling that will be varied depending on sample customers characteristics and wants as well. Most selling products for each superstore are:

- Khulshi Mart:** Cosmetics, Bakery;
- Well-Mart:** Fish and Meat, Cosmetics, Vegetables;
- Meena Bazar:** Bakery, Fish and Meat, Cosmetics and Groceries;
- Agora:** Bakery, Groceries, Fish and Meat, Cosmetics;
- Shwapno:** Vegetables, Cosmetics, Fish and Meat, Household, Fruits and Bakery.

1.5.3 Factors affecting consumers to shop at specific superstore [Table # 3]

The very first reason of sample customers to purchase from superstore is quality products, products variety and special products that are 66%, 54% and 52% respectively. The other reasons, by order based on percentages of the sample customers' preference, are location (48%), hygienic environment (46%), hassle free shopping and freshness (36%), competitive price (28%), service and layout of the store (24%). Some customers like to purchase baby food from the superstores as well. People those who came to purchase regularly from superstore don't use the home delivery option as where available. All the stores possess their specialty on gathering certain products by which some of the customer prefers purchasing from the particular store.

1.5.4 Rating Average by own customer [Table # 4]

All the customers are rated their shopping superstore very well, averaged between 71 to 83, out of 100. Actually they are rated against the usual services offered by the particular store. Above all, the customers of Agora are very satisfied according to the customers' responses that are 83% on an average.

1.5.5 Customer Opinion for offering poor brand mix of an individual product [Table # 5]

Most of the respondents are neutrally evaluating the brand mix of different products out of which the maximum no. goes to the customer of Shwapno (78%). The customers of Agora prefer disagree about offering poor brand mix of an individual product (82%). On an average all the stores maintain variety in individual product category that's why respondents prefer disagree, by order Meena Bazar-73%, Khulshi Mart-60%, Shwapno-22%, and Well Mart-38%. 12% and 9% of the customers of Well Mart and Meena Bazar strongly disagrees to poor brand mix.

1.5.6 Level of Customer Satisfaction based on intention to Repeat Purchase, Recommendation to others and Satisfaction [Table # 6]

In the data and analysis, customers are almost shown their preference as much as possible in the extreme level. The highly satisfied customers are in Meena Bazar (81%), and then Agora (78%), Shwapno (60%). The customers of Well Mart (34%) and Khulshi Mart (40%) are not highly satisfied but some of them are expected to be much better than existing.

1.6 Recommendation

More Outlets: If the superstore introduces more outlets at different places of the city, consumers tend to savor the neighborhood experience assuming more outlets more customers.

Change in Customer Lifestyle: The store sales will be increased day by day due to making changes in customers' lifestyle, taste and preferences.

Effective Supply Chain Management for low price offer: With prices of the perishable goods being offered below the prices of the nearby kitchen markets, it is hoped to convince customers to change the most of consumers shopping habits. In this regard company can introduce effective supply chain management to make products available in time and good networking system for direct source to get the products at maximum possible lowest cost from the farmers avoiding excessive middlemen cost and risk there to. Backward linkage can be the better way to consolidate the store image and position in order to secure a reliable supply of products identified the farmers who really grow products.

More Line of Product with More Promotion: The store can begin to catch up a slice of retailing and wholesale trade to ensure more product and full line of products with promotion.

Intensive Customer Service: To secure the position into the customers mind, promising intensive customer service and a variety of products assortment along with assuring customers of high standards and guarantees the correct weight in sales.

Digital Offerings: To launch E-commerce website to enhance customer satisfaction and induce the customers to get the benefit there to like finding desired products and have them delivered at home. It is expected that maintain the relationship with customer one step further and be nearer to them at all times.

Discount Card: They can initiate their own selling card so that customers can directly purchase the goods by using it and offer discount.

Avoid Service Charges, No More Price: They can provide the relief or in some cases some monetary benefit to take off the additional amount charges for vat and others which have already been paid by the company or inclusive into the retail price.

Be a Price Leader: To maintain and focus on price leadership in every market can be a better strategy to sustain and to ensure more sales with the motto of save people money so they can live better.

New Product Assortment: The store can begin to integrate sourcing capabilities to maintain variety of products assortment.

Everyday Low Pricing Strategy: They can bring in every day low prices (EDLP) philosophy under which products priced at a low price every day so that customers trust that product prices will not change under frequent promotional activity.

Promotional options for every bit: Introduce several promotional campaigns like value week, annual sales festival, and discount at bulk amount purchasing for increase sales and make distinction from other competing stores.

Quality and Freshness Again: To improve in food quality and freshness by using quality controls, better hygiene and correct storage conditions like cooling and refrigerating.

1.7 Conclusions

This report documented the demographic overview and customer profile of regular customers of superstores at Chittagong. Looking at the big picture that the data portrayed, we can conclude that, in spite some problems, the superstores movement overall worked relatively well. Though the superstore background history as much as not getting fruit from their targeted market, but the movement of competitors are being paid to make challenges for future by reducing prices to come closer and significantly differentiate the store one to another. By recompensing attention to cost-cutting trial and customer service, one can be exceeded expected profits, me-think. If it is possible to continue dedication to the employees' and the customers' needs and maintaining active involvement in the community, it will be very easy to get the early fruit as they like.

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Appendix

Table # 1(a): Sample Customers Demographic Profile (Age-wise sample participant)

Name of the store	Age						
	18-22	23-27	28-32	33-37	38-42	43-47	48+
Meena Bazar	-	4	5	1	1	-	-
Khulshi Mart	5	1	1	1	1	-	-
Shwapno	-	2	2	3	1	1	-
Agora	1	2	3	2	-	2	1
Well Mart	-	1	5	-	1	2	
TOTAL	6	10	16	8	4	5	1
% Based on total no. of customer	12	20	32	16	8	10	2

[Source: Field Survey]

Table # 1(b): Sample Customers Demographic Profile (Customers Qualification, Gender and Marital Status)

Academic level	% of Customer	Marital Status	% of customer	Gender	% of customer
HSC	24	Single	34	Male	26
Graduate	56	Married	66	Female	74
Post-Graduate	14	Total	100	Total	100
Others	6				

[Source: Field Survey]

Table # 1(c): Sample Customers Demographic Profile (Occupation, Credit Card Usage and Car Owns)

Occupation/ Profession	No. of customer (%)	Credit card usage	No. of Customer (%)	Car Owns	No. of Customer (%)
Student	26	Yes	28	YES	26
Housewife	48	No	72	NO	74
Private Service	16	Total	100	Total	100
Own Business	2				
Govt. Service	4				
Retired	2				
Others	2				
Total	100				

[Source: Field Survey]

Table # 1(d): Sample Customers Demographic Profile (Experience Customer Base, Purchase frequency in a typical week & Levels of income)

Name of the store	No. of Customer	Experience Customer Base				Age	No. of Respondents (in %)	Purchase Frequency in a typical week (%)						
		Less than 6 month (%)	6 Month to 1 Year (%)	1 to 2 Years (%)	More than 2 Years (%)			less than once	1 or 2 times	3 or 4 times	More than 4 times	No Response		
Meena Bazar	11	-	4	5 (45%)	2	18-22	12	10	2					
Khulshi Mart	10	2	5 (50%)	2	1	23-27	20	6	6	2	4	2		
Shwapno	9		2	4 (44%)	3	28-32	32	4	16	6	4	2		
Agora	9	4 (44%)	3 (33%)	2		33-37	16	8	4				4	
Well Mart	9	-	-	4 (45%)	5 (55%)	38-42	8		4	2			2	
TOTAL	48*	6	14	17	11	43-47	10		6		2	2		
		13%	29%	35%	23%	48+	2				2			
						Total	100	28	38	10	12	12		

[Source: Field Survey] * No response from 2 respondents

Table # 2: Mostly Purchasing Product from each super store
 [Source: Field Survey]

Name of the store	Mostly Purchasing Product from each super store										
	a) Household	b) Home appliance	c) Cosmetics and Toiletries	d) Meat & Fish	e) Fruits	f) Groceries	g) Dairy	h) Bakery	i) Vegetables	j) Jewelry	k) Others- Baby food
Meena Bazar	2		5	5	4	5	1	7	4		4
Khulshi Mart	2		7	3	2	2		6	2		1
Shwapno	5	3	7	6	5	3	2	5	9		
Agora			5	5	4	6	2	7			2
Well Mart	5	1	6	7	1	1	2	3	6		
TOTAL	14	4	30	26	16	17	7	28	21	0	7
% based preference on total no. of customer	28	8	60	52	32	34	14	56	42	0	14

Table # 3: Factors affecting consumers to shop at specific superstore

Levels of Income (in '000 tk.)	% based on total no. of customer
20-40	30%
40-60	32%
60-80	24%
80-100	6%
100+	8%
Total	100

Age (years)	Purchasing Reasons												
	(a) Product variety	(b) Location	(c) Special product (only found in the store)	(d) Quality Products	(e) Fair & Competitive prices	(f) Hassle-free shopping environment	(g) Hygienic	(h) Fresh vegetables, meat	(i) Service of the store personnel	(j) Home Delivery	(k) Layout of the Store	(l) Credit Purchase Facility	(m) Social Status
18-22	3	4	3	6	1	1	1	2	-	-	-	-	-
23-27	7	5	2	6	4	2	6	4	1	-	1	-	1
28-32	4	1	12	5	4	6	1	9	5	-	4	-	-
33-37	7	7	7	7	3	5	7	2	4	-	4	1	-
38-42	2	2	1	4	1	1	3	1	2	-	1	-	-
43-47	4	4	1	4	1	2	4	-	-	-	2	-	2
48+	-	1	-	1	-	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total Customer Responses	27	24	26	33	14	18	23	18	12	-	12	1	3
% based on total	54	48	52	66	28	36	46	36	24	0	24	2	6

[Source: Field Survey]

Table # 4 : Rating Average by own customer

Table # 5: Customer Opinion for offering poor

Name of the store	Rating Average by own customer (%)
Meena Bazar	79
Khulshi Mart	75
Shwapno	71
Agora	83
Well Mart	78

[Source: Field Survey]

brand mix of an individual product

Scales	Name of the store				
	Meena Bazar	Khulshi Mart	Shwapno	Agora	Well Mart
Strongly Agree	0	0	0	0	0
Agree	9	10	0	0	0
Neutral	9	30	78	18	50
Disagree	73	60	22	82	38
Strongly disagree	9	0	0	0	12

	Levels of Satisfaction				
	Meena Bazar	Khulshi Mart	Shopno	Agora	Well Mart
Very Satisfied	81	40	60	78	34
Satisfied	19	50	30	22	43
Good, but can be better	0	10	10	0	23
Dissatisfied	0	0	0	0	0
Very Dissatisfied	0	0	0	0	0

[Source: Field Survey]

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